

Architecture Considerations for ISAC in 6G

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Abstract—ISAC is emerging as a foundational capability in 6G, enabling mobile networks to not only offer communication services but also to sense and perceive their environment at scale. This paper explores architectural considerations to enable sensing in 6G, extending on recent developments by (pre-)standardisation bodies such as 3GPP and ETSI. Selected ISAC use cases are presented from the European MultiX project including associated potential functional system requirements. The paper proposes a 6G system architecture that integrates newly proposed NFs for the purpose of sensing and demonstrates how they are being used in offering sensing as a service. Protocol stack adaptations for both control and a newly proposed sensing plane are discussed.

Index Terms—ISAC, 6G System, Standardisation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Back in November 2023, International Telecommunication Union - Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R) released their International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT) 2030 vision framework [1] which provides six usage scenarios and four overarching aspects for the usage scenarios to build upon. Three usage scenarios out of the six were taken from ITU-R's 2020 vision, i.e. immersive communication (adopted from Enhanced Mobile Broadband in 5G), massive communication (adopted from Massive Machine Type Communication (mMTC) in 5G) and Hyper Reliable Low Latency Communication (adopted from Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communication in 5G). Additionally, ITU-R spells out three new usage scenarios in their 2030 vision, i.e. ubiquitous connectivity, AI and Communication, and Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC). This paper focuses on the Integrated Sensing and Communication usage scenarios and provides System Architecture (SA) considerations to enable this usage scenario in 6G Systems (6GSs) covering architectural and protocol SA aspects.

3GPP Technical Report (TR) 22.837 [2] provides consolidated potential functional requirements for ISAC categorised into general, configuration and authorisation, network exposure, security and charging. The performance requirements are provided as numerical values, clustered around three scenarios, specifically object detection and tracking, environment monitoring, and motion monitoring. Sensing specific performance requirements include confidence level, accuracy of

positioning, accuracy of velocity, sensing resolution, maximum sensing service latency, refresh rate, missed detection and false alarm. 3GPP then specifies the service requirements for ISAC-enabled 5G-Advanced systems in Technical Specification (TS) 22.137 [3], which provides terminology definitions for sensing and defined sensing operations in 3GPP systems supporting co-located and separated sensing receiver and transmitter and the processing of 3GPP sensing data inside the 3GPP system for objects outside of the 3GPP system.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section II provides a description of ISAC use cases considered in the MultiX project and identified as not covered in any standardisation body. This is followed by architectural considerations to enable ISAC in 6G Systems in Section III, providing foundational assumptions, an overview of what a Sensing Task is composed of in 6GSs and a revised SA. The paper is concluded in Section IV.

II. CONSIDERED USE CASES

In 2022, 3GPP SA1 started working on TR 22.837 as part of Release 19 which studied service requirements for ISAC in 5G in the form of use cases [2]. The technical report provides 32 ISAC use cases covering a wide range of applications. The application range includes object and intruder detection, collision avoidance and trajectory tracking, automotive navigation, public safety, rainfall monitoring, health and sports monitoring. Special considerations are provided on aspects of confidentiality, integrity and privacy, as well as regulatory requirements. This can be explained when comparing ISAC with technical advances in previous evolution of mobile networks, i.e., ISAC-enabled networks offer the ability to track and identify objects in the environment including their micro movements such as heart rates. If the resolution of sensing data is sufficiently high, sensing results could theoretically include visual profiles of humans and critical infrastructures; and as it is foreseen that sensing results may be exposed to trusted or untrusted third parties, causing data privacy and security concerns. Thus, 3GPP TR 22.837 spells out potential requirements around confidentiality and privacy protection, and data integrity when developing technical specifications that enable ISAC in mobile networks. In late 2024, 3GPP SA1 then started the study on 6G use cases and service requirements as a Release 20 technical report, i.e., TR 22.870 [4]. This report

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Fig. 1. Illustration of Shopping Experience Tracker Scenario Utilising sensing results from Multiple Mobile Network Operators.

provides considerations for system and operational aspects around migration to 6G, including security, sustainability and device support. These use cases are clustered around the IMT 2030 usage scenarios, i.e., Artificial Intelligence (AI), ISAC, Ubiquitous Connectivity and Massive Communication. This report also provides further use cases on industry and verticals. In the area of ISAC, the report comprises 13 approved use cases at the time of writing this article.

In 2024, the European Telecommunication Standardisation Institute (ETSI) Industry Specification Group (ISG) on ISAC released a Group Report (GR) 6G ISAC use cases [5]. The GR describes 18 advanced use cases ranging from human motion recognition and emergency rescue to autonomous vehicle navigation and industrial robotics. The GR also provides functional requirements and proposes new Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as fine motion accuracy and sensing service range, ensuring a robust performance evaluation framework for 6G sensing services. Some of the 3GPP 6G use cases in TR 22.870 on ISAC are presented in a more elaborate format in the ISG's GR. Also the 5G-ACIA collected ISAC use cases focussing on industrial applications [6].

A. Smart Shopping Tracker

This use case describes the ability for a third-party service provider to collect sensing results from multiple Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) leveraging 6G and non-6G sensing data. The Smart Shopping Tracker demonstrates the business opportunities of ISAC for MNOs and third-party service providers to offer novel services to existing sectors, e.g., the retail sector. The proposition is that a shop owner at a larger shopping mall is interested in customers' shopping behaviour. The store owner finds out about a company called SENSOR - not affiliated with the shopping mall or with any particular MNO - but offers a service to retailers to obtain customer shopping behaviour insights. This is conveyed as a 3D representation of the store's interior and a heatmap-like overlay showing the customer interest. The scenario is illustrated in Fig. 1. It is assumed that SENSOR has contracts with both MNOs have coverage at the shopping mall and have ISAC capabilities in their 6G networks. The retailer also acquired a broadband connection from MNO A and has

Fig. 2. Smart Home Use Case.

a sensing-enabled Wi-Fi Access Point (AP) in their shop. A number of store visitors are with either MNO A or B and their 6G devices are IEEE 802.11bf-enabled as well. The shop owner booked the service from SENSOR to obtain information about which products were of most interest to their customers. Once the shop owner had completed their contractual agreement, SENSOR issues a sensing service request to both MNOs providing the necessary information about the area to be sensed (e.g. cartesian coordinates of the shop outline), the desired KPIs for the sensing results, and the daily opening times of the store when sensing results should be provided. At store opening times, both MNOs start setting up their sensing activities to provide the sensing results SENSOR requested. Using the provided location of the store, both MNOs check for available User Equipments (UEs) in the sensing area for 6G UE-involved mono-, bi- and multi-static sensing. While continuously assessing the KPIs of the generated sensing results (mainly around target object identification confidence level and resolution accuracy), MNO B's network determines that the sensing result KPIs have not been met and consults a trusted Application Function (AF) for assistance information to utilise Wi-Fi sensing of UEs, provisioned by MNO B's shops, located inside the sensing area. Using the identifiers of the UEs provided by the MNO's network, the AF reaches out to each UE that is capable of performing Wi-Fi sensing to provide results using the shopping mall's deployed Wi-Fi-enabled APs. In contrast, MNO A has the ability to complement 6G sensing data with Wi-Fi sensing data from the Wi-Fi AP the store deployed to offer a potentially better sensing service continuity.

B. Smart Home

This use case exemplifies how ISAC technology can create new business opportunities for MNOs and service providers allowing them to offer new services for the smart home sector. The proposition is that a home owner wishes to be informed of intruders (person or harmful animal), outside or inside their private property. Currently, this is achieved by utilising IP/CCTV cameras, passive infrared sensors and microwave radars capable of monitoring and detecting objects and/or motion. However, these sensors either require Line of Sight (LOS) or their monitoring area capabilities are limited and they can be easily accessed and damaged by malicious intruders. Wireless signals provided by 6G Base Stations (BSs), Wi-Fi Customer Premises Equipment (CPE) and UEs with sensing capabilities make it possible to monitor wider areas in a more

robust and secure manner. In addition, the fusion of the sensing data of 6G and non-6G wireless devices can improve accuracy and ubiquity of the intruder detection service. It is considered that a home owner is a subscriber to a certain telecom provider and the home owner is informed about a new security service, called SENSE, which can provide them with a virtual security system that does not require the home owner to install any equipment or sensors to their premise. SENSE is based on the new sensing capabilities provided by the telecom provider (6G BSs, Wi-Fi CPEs and 6G UEs). With SENSE, the home owner will receive tamper-proof sensing information from the outdoor base stations, covering the entire outdoor area with high accuracy and no blind spots. The telecom provider will also upgrade the home owner's Wi-Fi CPE and UEs with ones supporting sensing functionality, allowing them to receive high-accuracy sensing information also for the indoor of the house, again with high accuracy and no blind spots. Therefore, the home owner will be notified of both outdoor and indoor intruders, along with knowing their exact location. The scenario of how the new service SENSE works is illustrated in Fig. 2. Outdoor coverage is provided by a 6G BS with sensing capabilities while indoor coverage is provided by a Wi-Fi CPE and one or more UEs. The SENSE service will also be able to support the home owner's 6G and Wi-Fi wireless cameras (optional), both outside and inside the premises. The home owner will be able to designate the outdoor surveillance area, so whenever the sensing function of the BS detects an intruder within the surveillance area, the home owner will be notified via push notifications or SMS so that they can decide on their next actions. Indoor intruders can be detected by the sensing function of the Wi-Fi CPE and/or UEs. Due to the motion of an indoor human, the 6G sensing signal measured by the UEs and the sensing signal of the Wi-Fi CPE will be influenced. By analysing and collecting the sensing information, such as Doppler frequency shift, amplitude or phase change, the behaviour of an indoor human could be detected. Similar services can also be provided by third party service providers who can obtain the necessary sensing results, after signing contracts with one or more telecom operators.

C. Collaborating Robots in Smart Factories

In this use case, robots work collaboratively on an industrial task. They are supported by means of a multi-layer Digital Twin (DT) and of sensing capabilities of different kinds. Each robot is equipped with specific sensors tailored to perform certain functions. However, the challenge lies in the fact that these robots, when operating individually, lack the comprehensive capability and information required to perform the industrial task successfully. The primary goal is to enable a group of collaborating robots to perform a task that surpasses their individual capabilities and to allow each robot to perceive its environment beyond its local sensory limitations. The industrial environment delivers various sensor information, that provides context information for different areas (e.g. different robots may have different sensing ranges) and topics (e.g. sensors for ranging vs. sensors for measuring radio

Fig. 3. Collaborating Robots in Smart Factories Use Case.

channel characteristics). The various sensor information may feed different DTs, such as an Environment DT, a Network DT, and an Application DT. This is where the concept of a multi-layer DT comes into play. Like the robots, each DT on its own lacks the capability to provide the full context necessary for the industrial application or communication service. The multi-layer DT combines the individual DTs to create a comprehensive view, that enables the identification and resolution of potential issues, improves decision-making, and allows for dynamic adaptations and reconfiguration of the industrial application or network, based on specific circumstances and predicted events. Especially, it can provide the aggregated sensing results to the collaborating robots. This enhances the sensing capabilities of the individual robots and supports them in their collaboration and in other tasks that benefit from environmental information acquired by sensing methods. Fig. 3 shows an example scenario for collaborating robots in a smart factory. Robot B has to move to Robot A in order to work collaboratively on a task. The different local sensing results of both robots are aggregated in the multi-layer DT. The aggregated sensing information provides guidance for the movement of Robot B, e.g. path routing, detection of obstacles, optimal connectivity. Robot B can now see beyond the wall that hides Robot A, it can determine a path around the wall, and the sensing information in the multi-layer DT is used to provide reliable connectivity with the needed QoS by dynamically reconfiguring, for instance, the reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS) in Fig. 3.

III. ARCHITECTURAL CONSIDERATIONS

This section presents the architectural proposition on how to enable ISAC in a 6GS. The section is structured around foundational assumptions for 6GS, followed by how sensing services are envisaged to be fulfilled by a 6GS. This baseline then is leveraged to provide architecture considerations on how to enable ISAC in a 6GS, split between a refined and extended Control Plane (CP) and newly proposed Sensing Plane (SP).

A. Foundational Assumptions for 6G Systems

While the architectural 6G specification work has not started in 3GPP's SA Working Group 2 (SA2) Working Group

Fig. 4. Considered Sensing Workflow in 6G Systems

(WG), a range of propositions have been made in European Commission (EC)-funded research projects [7], [8] and pre-standardisation fora [9]. Key architectural principles for 6GS have been identified:

Modularity: With 5G Rel.15, 3GPP adopted Service-Based Architecture (SBA) principles for its Core Network (CN) which allows to deploy the majority of all 5G Network Functions (NFs) in a truly cloud-native fashion. Such paradigm shift allows operators to scale a 5G CN on-demand either based on load or failover scenarios of NF instances. To achieve such scalable CN 3GPP disintegrated 4G's Evolved Packet Core (EPC) from three NFs into NFs with a smaller set of functionalities. Such a modular approach allows functionality to be decoupled from each other and MNOs the flexibility to only deploy the functionality that interests them. It is desired by operators to enable such scalable CN for all NFs in 6G.

Simplicity: Operators have expressed their strong desire for 6G not to have multiple architectural options, as it was done for 5G with the two modes non-standalone and standalone. Building on top of a single 6G architecture, interface and protocol choices on all planes should be further unified paving the way for a fully cloud-native 6G system.

Sustainability: The environmental impact should be further reduced in 6G, with a strong focus on energy consumption and architectural enablers to achieve that. Radio, networking, compute and storage resources should be able to utilise more efficiently and optimised on-demand where needed. Economic sustainability and environmental sustainability are the key priority for the architecture of future-proof 6G, which should be enabled by cost-effective deployment and operations with less energy consumed and efficient use of all types of resources.

Network-as-a-Service: As in 5G, services offered by a 6GS should be exposed by a common Application Programming Interface (API) with any newly added service offering around the IMT 2030 usage scenarios leveraging the same principles.

B. Sensing Service Workflow

The workflow for sensing in a 6GS is depicted in Fig. 4 and is based on ETSI's ISG ISAC GR on use cases and requirements [5]. The workflow shows functional blocks and the sensing information flow across them.

The functional blocks have the following meanings: **Sensing signal** is a transmitted signal from a sensing transmitter for the purpose of sensing. The signal can be 6G or non-6G. Examples of a sensing signal are RF-based approaches or light for triggering sensors in cameras and LiDAR. A **Sensing Transmitter** is a 6G or non-6G entity that transmits a sensing signal. An **Sensing Receiver** is a 6G or non-6G entity that receives a sensing signal and produces sensing measurements. An Sensing Receiver (SRX) can be co-located with an Sensing Transmitter (STX). **Sensing data** is the 6G or non-6G data produced for sensing purposes. The **sensing data generation** step is a UE or Access Networks (ANs) functionality to take In-phase and Quadrature (I/Q) or Channel State Information (CSI) data from the SRX and generate sensing data. A **sensing service** is a feature of the 6GS that is offered to service consumers. A Sensing Service provides sensing results based on communicated requirements and KPIs. A **Sensing Task (ST)** consists of activities to perform sensing, including the configuration of the required STXs and SRXs (if applicable), the collection of sensing data, the processing of the sensing data and the exposure of the sensing results. Each ST fulfils a Sensing Service request. A **Target Sensing Service Area (TSSA)** is a 2- or 3-dimensional cartesian location area described with relative or absolute cartesian points that need to be sensed by deriving characteristics of the environment and/or objects within the environment with certain sensing quality from the impacted (e.g. reflected, refracted, diffracted) sensing signals. The **sensing results** may include characteristics of objects (e.g. type, distance, velocity, trajectory, size, shape, material), or other contextual information (e.g. time of generation, environmental information) about objects in the TSSA. Note, it is not precluded that the sensing result exposed to an entity within 6GS or to a third party may in some cases consist of the sensing data itself. **Fusion** refers to a process to join two or more streams of sensing data or sensing results together to form one or more sensing data or sensing result stream(s). Fusion can take place at the origin of the sensing data, or along the system entities of a 6GS, and in some cases in non-6GS entities. The fusion of sensing results can also take place with all 6GS system entities (i.e. UE, AN, CN). The **exposure** process coordinates the Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting (AAA) of third-party components to request and retrieve sensing results from the 6GS.

C. Sensing-Enabled 6G System Architecture

This section presents System Architecture considerations for an ISAC-enabled 6GS. These considerations are rooted in ongoing system research work of the EC-funded MultiX project, with insights from the 3GPP, the recent 5G-A SA Stage 2 study on ISAC and work within the ETSI ISG ISAC.

Fig. 5 illustrates SA considerations on how to enable ISAC in a 6GS. For readers well versed in 5G, the illustrated system architecture builds upon an SBA proposition in the CN where system functionality is disintegrated into different NFs for the purpose of multi-vendor deployments, the ability to scale

Fig. 5. Considered 6G System Architecture with support for 6G and non-6G Sensing.

on demand and the ability to choose not to deploy certain system functionality. To enable ISAC, there is no difference to this proposition and new NFs are proposed for 6G. Before delving into their purpose, one may notice the disappearance of the Access and Mobility Function (AMF) from the SA; with a range of key contributions to 3GPP calling out the limitations of deploying the CN in a truly cloud-native fashion where no NF has a mix of service- and non-service-based interfaces, e.g. the AMF. As a result, the SBA bus is extended down to the AN, enabling a Service-Based Interface (SBI) towards the AN, i.e. N_{AN} . The newly proposed ISAC-related NFs are listed below in alphabetical order and described in their functionalities for the purpose of offering a 6GS sensing service:

Sensing Coordination Function (SCF): This NF is responsible for the coordination of establishing, modifying and terminating STs. SCF is coordinating this in close relationship with the AN to select the ST Group (STG) members (UEs, ANs, AFs) based on their capabilities, availability and utilisations for 6G and non-6G sensing sources. This includes assistant information towards the AN on selecting the most appropriate sensing mode for the successful ST execution. SCF also manages sensing mobility of target objects while working closely with the AMF for UE mobility scenarios where the UE is either an STX, SRX or both.

Sensing Processing Functions (SPF): This NF collects, processes, fuses and stores sensing data from SRXs. Processing and fusion may leverage AI techniques and the SPF may offer capabilities for model training, storage and inference. The SPF outputs sensing results.

Sensing Exposure Function (SEF): This NF is responsible for exposing sensing results from the SPF to 6GS third party components. Key AAA functionalities also resides in the SEF for ISAC-related purposes.

Non-6G ANs are of great use to complement limitations of sensing-enabled 6G ANs, as described in the use case provided in Section II-A. To enable the 6GS to coordinate Wi-Fi sensing of trusted and untrusted non-6G ANs, Fig. 5 illustrates the 5G components Trusted Non-3GPP Access Network (TNAN) and Non-3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF) offering an SBI of their own for the SCF to leverage them to execute an ST.

Besides extending the SBA to all system components, apart from the UE, Fig. 5 also illustrates a SP. In comparison to the traditional User Plane (UP) between the UE and the

Data Network (DN) via the AN and UP Function (UPF), the SP allows sensing data to be exchanged between system components that either produce sensing results (i.e. the SPF) and share/expose them (i.e. SPF and optionally SEF depending on the Sensing Service Consumer (SSC)) or forward the sensing data to system components (i.e. SPF) to process and fuse sensing data for the purpose of generating sensing results eventually. As the system components to achieve the generation of sensing results are not in the DN, the need for a dedicated SP is deemed necessary to enable Quality of Service (QoS) enforcement over the exchange of sensing data and sensing results to meet the requested sensing service KPIs.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

As 6G continues to evolve, ISAC is poised to become a cornerstone of next-generation mobile systems, facilitating not only communication but also environmental awareness across diverse application domains. This paper presented key architectural and protocol enhancements required to support ISAC in 6G, grounded in real-world use cases from the MultiX project. By identifying functional requirements and proposing dedicated network functions and planes, a cohesive vision of how ISAC can be systematically integrated into a cloud-native, service-based 6G CN is provided. The proposed architecture emphasises modularity to support advanced sensing services while maintaining compatibility with both 6G and non-6G sensing technologies. These insights aim to guide future standardisation efforts and support the scalable deployment of ISAC-enabled services in 6G systems.

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